

New European Bauhaus Academy

1st New European Bauhaus Academy Conference

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NEB and Place-making in the NEB Sud Hub

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Univesity of Genoa

Beatrice Zerega
Regione Liguria

Circular Bio-based Europe

Joint Undertaking

Co-funded by the European Union

NEB ACADEMY HUBS: first achievements and success stories

NEB «Sustainable Design with wood and bio-based materials” NEB SUD Hub

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Università
di **Genova**

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LIFE BE-WoodEN Buildings and Education in Wood Ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus

Skills, competences and training (long life CP)

/ 22 webinars, 18 speakers, 47 hours Italian and European platforms linked to professional training

/ NEB and placemaking PWR

/ Green and circular construction UNIGE, ART-ER, UP

/ Use of wood in construction UNIFI

/ 8 Podcast in English and 8 Italian available on Spotify FLA

1.686 users (IT)

304 users (EN) increasing

653 users

Lamination and strength classes

Combined Glulam
can not be used in horizontal, as glulam elements (↓) for load-bearing floors.

Glulam for floors can be produced with tongue and groove.

BEAM-BEAM-WALL CONNECTION

Fissaggio travi affiancate-parete interna
Verifica della connessione tra travi affiancate di copertura e pareti interne come previste per il Blocco B1.

Dettaglio T3 dell'elaborato "502_Pianta pareti X-Lam e particolari costruttivi".

Foto: P. Simeone
Drawings: Kieiko/XLD

Fai il montaggio in cantiere, sopravelazione Blocco B1
Check trave-parete:
- viti Rothoblaas HBS 8x200
- passo 15 cm
- cucitura con fissaggio delle viti inclinate e alternate lato interno-lato esterno
Check trave-trave:
- viti Rothoblaas HBS 8x300
- passo 15 cm
- cucitura con fissaggio delle viti inclinate su lato interno ed esterno

Innovative training

- / WP3-4 results – Winter School in Florence, testing laboratories and visiting wood companies
20 people, *DAGRI Department organized by UNIFI* <https://youtu.be/TMcLTzXL8Bg>
- / study visit in Slovenia, *Innorennew CoE, Izola* and *Stilles Company, Slovenia*, 28 people
organized by UP <https://youtu.be/VsOzARsjxzw>

Innovation Laboratory and Challenge Based Learning

<https://youtu.be/uiy6v1PPpbk>

- / Applying the principles of the NEB Compass, co-participatory and interdisciplinary design approaches, with a specific focus on social housing
- / WP4 results – Testing on a real case, Challenge Based Learning among architects, artisan, social innovators, artist (mixed groups, 48 p. and 8 projects) – renovation of common spaces

Implementation

<https://youtu.be/2lqdQydlPEk>

Self-construction workshop

<https://youtu.be/Vu7U8Wo3vXA>

Dissemination and exploitation

- / Education institutions through European Association for Architectural Education *EAAE*
- / Councils and professionals Association (*ACE and CNAPPC*)
- / Number of *Professional Credits Certifications* already issued for BE-WoodEN webinars and Nebinars (Italy): *9.880*
- / Local, regional and municipal administrations, natural park authorities
- / Housing providers associations and social housing users (*Housing Europe and Federcasa*)
- / Business associations, clusters, companies (*through FLA and Art-ER*)
- / Citizens and local associations

Project Leader

Partner

NEB and Place-making in the NEB Sud Hub

Beatrice Zerega, Regione Liguria

February 27th, 2026 | Barcelona, Spain

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Place-making and place-maker

Who is the place-maker?

Hybrid figure, such as the citizen-traveler, the mayor-environmentalist, artist-entrepreneur and not just architects, engineers and designers, who transform our cities and ideas that become projects

 Place Designer

- Use of Nature Based Solutions;
- Reforestation;
- Restoration of ecosystems;
- Integration of nature into urban contexts;
- Social interactions and cultural aspects

Place-making and place-maker

FRAGILITY

CREATIVITY

Place-making and place-maker

KEY ASPECTS of place-making:

1. Multidisciplinary
2. Innovation;
3. Dialogue with communities and citizens;
4. NEB Strategy, its values and its working principles;
5. Involvement of Public administrations and officers
6. Importance of promoting **new education and training methodologies;**

Life BE-WoodEN project

(<https://lifebewooden.unige.it/it>) has promoted the so-called «NEBinars» that, thanks to training courses, both theoretical and practical experiences, best practices and analysis of successful initiatives, aim **to empower designers to evolve into place-makers**, enabling them to undertake NEB projects at the local level

Place-making and place-maker, the LIFE BE-WoodEN experience in the Ligurian territory

1. Innovation Lab (October 2024 – March 2025)

- *Expression of interest* for the engagement in the workshops of artists, craftsmen, experts in social inclusion, social engagement, professionals (architects, engineers, construction companies) → 48 (18 experts and 30 professionals) divided into **8 heterogeneous and multidisciplinary groups** and involved in the Challenge Based Learning (CBL)
- *Matching workshop*, where interdisciplinary groups were formed to brainstorm and develop innovative solutions for the future of housing
- *Two-days innovative design workshop (Innovation Lab)*
 - NEB approach
 - NEB Compass
 - Visit to the social housing building
 - Neighborhood involvement

Place-making and place-maker, the LIFE BE-WoodEN experience in the Ligurian territory

2. Self-construction workshop (October – November 2025)

Winning project → «Multipurpose socio-cultural space»

- Analysis of the **needs** of the residents, inhabitants of the neighborhood and stakeholders;
- NEB values and working principles application;
- Reinforcement of **the sociality of residents** and **active participation**;
- Use of sustainable and natural materials;
- **Participatory process**, involvement of students and volunteers, and local communities;
- Reappropriation of common spaces;
- Sustainability over time, by community management

PLACE-MAKING: implementation of key elements in the reality of a neighborhood that becomes *a public space open to all the neighborhood's inhabitant*

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Consortium

Thank you!
